

Are Social Network Services Risky?

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Abstract: Online communication technology has appeared as a blessing, opening doors for individuals and at the same time for institutions even in this critical global economic era. This was further facilitated by the major shift in consumers' attitude in favor of online social networking. This type of networking transcended the limitations of traditional social networking structure but sometimes at a cost of distortion of the social values and significant negative impacts on consumers and the society at large. Bangladesh has newly adopted this online technology with a significant lack of technological readiness among the people and concerned institutions. In this paper I discuss about the online social networking, its relevant impacts on different dimensions, and some probable way outs users might consider to minimize the negative impacts.

Keywords: social network services, Facebook, social value, risks of social network

Introduction

As technology matures diverse applications emerge in market. Due to innovative utility features global consumers accept the technology diffusion with increasing interest. One of the miracles of technological innovation pool is internet. With the incredible pace of science and technology, innovation has also got different dimensions and today's internet technology along with its numerous applications is a vivid proof of that. Social network service (SNS) or social networking site or online social networking is an unparalleled technological innovation reshaping the aspects of social value system and business intelligence for the last five years.

SNS implies communication between groups of people generally mediated by internet technologies through computers, mobile phones and personal digital assistants. Generally SNS creates interfaces through websites that resemble online communities of people who either share interests and activities, or are interested in exploring interests and activities of others. Among all such sites Facebook, Myspace, LinkedIn, Youtube, twitter, Orkut, Hi5, Flickr and Livejournal are the most popular ones among netizens. Netizen is a member of the community of internet users, especially those who spend a large portion of their life online. SNS provides a new avenue for maintaining social relationships, finding users with similar interests, and locating contents and knowledge contributed or endorsed by other users.

The remarkable growth of SNS across the world poses a clear indication that digital technologies are radically changing communications landscape and people, specifically the younger generation netizens have become so engrossed in it that within a very short

time it has thrown a challenge to the channel effectiveness of the traditional television media (UNESCO, 2008). Availability of cheaper technology and communication, and rapid growth of telecommunication infrastructure have been fueling this SNS proliferation. According to com-Score (2009), a global leader in internet audience monitoring, 211 million people accounting for approximately three-quarters of all internet-users use SNS on regular basis.

Active users of SNS spend hours on internet working and socializing, and among many this has become a virtually indispensable form of communication. According to facebook.com (2009) globally more than eight billion minutes are spent on facebook each day. Due to increasing involvement of different types of consumers SNS has created innovative avenue for harvesting business opportunities as well. Search engine marketing, affiliate programs, web advertisements, collaborative filtering and many more have opened doors of endless opportunities for business. Although SNS platform is also criticized for undermining privacy and technological exploitation through abuse, it plays an important role in the life of its active users from social, psychological and business point of views. European Economic and Social Committee (Liz, 2009) have identified some positive aspects of SNSs focusing specifically their contribution to: (i) guaranteeing freedom of expression in certain social and political situations; (ii) developing and linking online communities; (iii) finding and meeting friends and family members and providing them with the opportunity to communicate with one another; (iv) preventing situations that entail risks for minors and enabling minors to ask for help through SNS, and (v) promoting goods and services and boosting e-commerce. Nevertheless the risks identified include: (i) psychological trauma caused by insults communicated by means of such services; (ii) sexual harassment of children and young; (iii) posting of photographs or videos of naked or semi-naked adolescents, either by themselves or by others; (iv) explicit advertisements for prostitution and 'escort' services; (v) frequent breaches of privacy, reputation and personal dignity; (vi) attacks on physical and mental wellbeing of site users; (vii) incitement to violence, racism and xenophobia; (viii) dissemination of totalitarian ideologies which are fascist in nature or advocate Nazism; and (ix) suicides by young people, allegedly as a result of certain intimate details being made public through these networks.

Objective

The major objectives of my paper are: (i) to introduce the concept of SNS to the readers, (ii) to discuss concerned issues and aspects of SNS, (iii) to analyze the significant impacts of SNS, (iv) to explore controversial issues of Facebook, and (v) to present some recommendations for a safer use of SNS.

Methodology

I used secondary data as the main data source and incorporated my experiences and understanding while correlating the findings to explain issues for Bangladesh. The secondary data sources I considered include recognized journals, articles, conference

papers, institutional reports, news paper and web publications from recognized web sources. While data extracting and synthesizing I used rules of thumb wherever it appeared required. In a nutshell, I followed a qualitative approach in discussing my topic and concerned issues and mostly document analysis accompanied by my observations helped me do that.

There exists almost no relevant research on the topic of this paper considering Bangladesh as the research area. Therefore I had to use peer groups' research findings. As the concerned technology is a global issue and the platform is exactly the same around the world transcending cultural and geographical boundaries hence findings and issues on peer groups in different areas of the world were considered. This appears reasonable as in case of online issues it is the whole globe that the technology can reach that should be considered as home ground or locality. I also focused a specific social networking site, Facebook, to facilitate understanding the issues as it is equally famous in Bangladesh and in other countries that I considered for collecting secondary data.

Review of the Literature

J.C.R. Licklider from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) developed a concept of 'Galactic Network' in 1962 where he envisaged that the entire world would be technologically connected to each other and to unlimited amounts of data (Hanlon, 2009). Today's innovative business usage of attention economy (sources of information are infinite but actual access is limited by individual human capacity) and the trend of shifting our social life to the internet are even a step ahead of such prediction.

SNS started its journey in the form of generalized online communities such as 'the Well' in 1985, 'Theglobe.com' in 1994, 'Geocities' in 1994 and 'Tripod' was introduced in 1995. These communities brought people together through chat rooms and personal homepage publishing tools that was a precursor to today's blogging phenomenon. During 2002 to 2004 three social networking sites emerged as the most popular ones and globally became part of the mainstream users. The first one was Friendster that Google tried to acquire in 2003, then MySpace and Bebo joined the market consecutively and the phenomenal Facebook emerged in 2004 with a rapid growth rate (Rosenbush, 2005). SNS flourished as a component of internet business strategy in 2005 when Yahoo launched Yahoo! 360°.

SNSs can be classified into two broad categories: internal social networking (ISN) and external social networking (ESN). An ISN is a closed or private community of a group of people within a company, association, society, education provider, organization or even an 'invite only' group created by a user in an ESN. An ESN like MySpace, Facebook, Twitter or Bebo is open or public that is available to all web users and usually is designed to attract advertisers. Recently SNS has become a warmly accepted work tool among different NGOs to create and promote awareness, to manage operations and administrations and to raise funds. Generally two types of SNSs are used: (i) house social network that is built on an NGO's own website and (ii) commercial social network that is

owned and operated by a corporation (Moshman, 2009). According to a survey five commercial social networks are mostly used by the NGOs and those are Facebook, Youtube, Twitter, LinkedIn and MySpace (Moshman, 2009).

Social science researchers have found that identity (Boyd, 2006), privacy (Gross and Acquisti, 2005), e-learning (Mazer, Murphy and Simonds, 2007), social capital (Ellison, Steinfield and Lampe, 2007) and teenage use (Boyd, 2007) are the most significant issues of SNS. Sociologists have studied many properties of SNS and found insightful information. For instance, Milgram (1967) identifies that average path length between two Americans is six hops, and Pool and Kochen (1978) provide an analysis of the small-world effect. Granovetter's (1982) argument that a social network can be partitioned into strong and weak ties, and that strong ties are tightly clustered, provides significant insight for marketers to utilize their data mining output from customer database in an effective manner, although ethical consideration of the process of collecting data might sometimes appear contradictory. According to Girvan and Newman (2002) users in online social networks tend to form tightly knit groups and this finding has become a spirit for the internet marketers.

Common Types of SNS

Increasing pace of development in communication technology and innovation in software development resulted in many new SNSs and different versions of existing SNSs that are now availed by increasing number of users around the world. SNSs are organized around users and typically provide a variety of ways to interact through chat, messaging, email, video, voice chat, file-sharing, blogging, and discussion groups. Members of SNSs publish their profiles and desired contents and create links to other users with whom they want to associate. General characteristics of a SNS are presented pictorially in the following figure 1.

Figure 1: Characteristics of SNS

Source: (Cachia, 2008)

Among the mostly used SNSs I presented brief notes on Facebook, MySpace, Twitter, and LinkedIn.

Facebook: This social utility was created in February 2004. Facebook, Inc. privately owns it and generally people join this SNS organized by city, school, and region to interact with other members. It develops technologies that facilitate sharing of information through social graph and digital mapping of people's real-world social connections. Users can add friends, send messages, create their own pages, post pictures and many other things. Earlier it was open only to university and college students but now allows free access to anyone 13 years old or older than that. Currently it has more than 350 million (Facebook, 2010) active users worldwide. In this SNS, 50% of its active users log on while more than 35 million users update their status each day. On an average a user has 130 friends on the site, sends eight friend requests per month and spends more than 55 minutes per day on Facebook. More than 70 translations are available on the site to cover diverse ethnic groups. To cope up with the recent proliferation of mobile use it has developed a mobile device compatible version and currently there are more than 65 million active users who access Facebook through their mobile devices and it is almost 50% more than the number of non-mobile active users. Apart from the general social networking interfaces Facebook also offers other applications and to harvest the direct access to users it has several innovative business solutions for internet marketers.

MySpace: It was inaugurated in August 2003. It is very interactive and allows users to create a network of friends, profiles, blogs, groups, music, pictures, and videos. MySpace requires users to be at least 14 years of old and profiles of youth under the age of 16 are automatically set to 'private' so that they cannot be found with a general search and under aged are not abused. In 2006 it was the most popular networking site in the United States of America but was internationally overtaken by Facebook in 2008. Like Facebook it also has versions that can be used in mobile devices.

Twitter: Jack Dorsey created it in 2006. It is also popular as the 'SMS of the Internet'. Twitter is a social networking and microblogging service that enables users to send and read messages known as tweets. Tweets are text-based posts of up to 140 characters displayed on the author's profile page and delivered to the author's subscribers who are known as followers. Users can send and receive tweets via the Twitter website, Short Message Service (SMS) or some external applications. Although the service itself costs nothing to use but accessing it through SMS might incur phone service provider fees. Currently it has more than 32 million active users.

LinkedIn: Unlike other popular SNSs, LinkedIn generally focuses on creating and keeping professional contacts. Since the year 2003, when it was launched, it has been allowing users to search for jobs, offering resources for hiring employees, and even been maintaining a special category dedicated to nonprofits. It has spanned in about 170 industries and has more than 40 million users.

Common Tools of SNS

Generally chat room, instant messaging and blogs are the most frequently used tools in SNSs although every day new and innovative tools and utilities are added by the SNSs. A chat room is a place online where people join to chat. Sometimes users can post profiles with pictures and other files and can even interface a web camera. Although Wolak, Mitchell and Finkelhor (2006) found that many youth described chat rooms as unpleasant places attracting unsavory people but in many places it is a popular platform among the people. Instant messaging (IM) is another real-time communication tool that allows two or more people who use the same IM service. In contrast to chat rooms, which are open to all, IM messages are sent through identifying names and hence the sender must know the identifying name of the recipient while sending the message. Some IM services offer member directories where users can create profiles that might include pictures and other information. Blogs are like online journals that people use as diaries or to comment on specific topics. Blogs can include detailed descriptions of personal experiences or feelings on any issue. Communication among known and unknown persons is allowed in many blogs and this is one good reason for its increasing popularity. SNS includes all these three tools and sometimes some more to position itself among the diversified users. Most of the SNSs enable users to create and join special interest groups. Users can post messages to groups and upload shared content. Some groups are administered by moderators whereas some are unrestricted.

Technical Aspects of SNS Trends

“...The First Law of Technology says - we invariably overestimate the short-term impact of new technologies while underestimating their longer-term effects.”
(Naughton, 2008:1)

The platform of SNS is internet that even before 2000 was very much the domain of the minority; wealthier people in poorer countries, and the tech-savvy in the developed world. But there have been significant changes since 2000 and online activity has transcended our everyday lives as we now communicate, learn, shop, search, study, bank, and socialize online. Users in the developing countries are increasingly getting around the issue of broadband rental costs. For instance, in South Africa the number of internet users through mobile phone is almost double than that of through desktop computers although in Brazil the scenario is different due to higher charges. Incredible global increase in mobile use and developments in mobile communication system have opened doors for SNSs to reach and connect people more effectively and consistently. Mobile phone charges are significantly lower than the rental cost of a landline or broadband in many developing countries like Thailand, India and Bangladesh.

An interesting feature of the digital spaces is the astonishing scale of innovation. This innovation is not constrained by the formal institutional research and development

endeavors rather many innovative contributions are coming from thousands of individuals working personally or with some venture capitalists. Thus it is really hard to say whether the centrally directed resources that produced the iPhone are more disruptive and long lasting than the garage-started Google. However, the only certain prediction is that there will be many generations of new systems and technologies in future, and we will only recognize the defining trends in retrospect. So, new trends to emerge in course of time should be treated as a normal phenomenon but among the existing ones – (i) platform convergence, (ii) mobile phone applications, (iii) mobile window on the web, (iv) mobile access to the wealth of the web, and (v) location-based services; are likely to continue and influence the development of SNS in the short and medium term.

Behavioral Aspects of SNS Trends

SNS has become more strategic and adaptive with the advancement of communication technology and consistently increasing dependency on internet and technology both in social and business arena. Innovative data mining techniques and advanced level software embedded with enriched artificial intelligence programs have facilitated providing a platform well tuned with the dynamic consumer behavior and human behavior at large. During the last two decades we have seen tremendous changes in society, driven by the information and communication technologies (ICT). From email and web to Facebook and Twitter, the processes of building and strengthening social relationships have been transformed resulting new forms of community.

Internet, the platform of SNSs, is mostly a male-dominated domain, both in case of computer and mobile access while generally females are found to be very active in sending SMS. In South Africa there was a 3.2% rise in the number of male internet users during December 2007 to December 2008 with 16% more male than female users in 2008. However, this trend is particularly evident in most of the developing countries like India and Bangladesh as opposed to the greater gender balance found in the developed countries like UK. Greater inequalities in developing countries in terms of access to education and participation in decision making might have been causing this disparity. Again, internet users are spread across the age spectrum with differing trends in different countries. For instance, half of India's urban internet users fall into 18 to 35 years age category, quite similar to figures for South Africa, but a larger proportion than in the UK. Most of the users who access internet via mobile phones are generally younger than those who access via personal computers.

A favorable demographic fact for the SNSs is - globally one in every five people can speak English to some level of competence. This trait facilitates having a good number of potential users, many of whom even view English as an aspirational language. But majority of the existing users of internet in the developing countries prefer it to be in their own language. For instance, in India, majority of the people use English on internet but

only 28% prefer it and the rest prefer to have it in their own language. In the spirit of meeting such diverse expectations intelligently, SNSs have started different lingual support in the same platform.

Many people, specifically those who are still not the users of any SNS, are concerned about the extent to which people are open and forthcoming about aspects of their private lives on SNS. However, Ewen Williams, the founder of both Blogger and Twitter, believes that a life lived openly is more authentic. Although, it is true that such openness challenges many aspects of traditional cultures but it certainly is a platform in which it might appear easier to challenge stereotypes and discuss controversial issues in public spaces.

In a SNS people can communicate with one another in a variety of ways using different points of contact and interest. Users join groups or online communities according to cultural or religious affiliation, hobbies, sports, politics or others. Sometimes users belong to several groups and communities at the same time, which results mass movements on the SNS. These common features of SNS have been facilitating a finer level of segmentation enriched with business insights. To harvest from this affiliation among different people marketers have been using collaborative filtering technique for online marketing to reach the target customers effectively using SNSs as the platform.

Some traits of the netizens of this generation who are active in SNS can be figured out by the volume of pictures, songs, profile pages, subversive art and other expressions available online. They are more media literate than previous generations and also expect similar rich communications. But the surprising coexistence of diverse tastes among the users of SNSs can be assumed by the activities of the Facebook fatigue group on Facebook that encourages people to log off permanently (Sorensen, 2008).

How Risky is SNS?

The root of SNS lies in internet and computer system and computer technology introduced several social changes in the world. I will not present any decisive approach regarding whether SNS is risky or not as that is a highly controversial issue, rather I will try to explore the positive and negative sides of SNS and focus the risks embedded in SNS that the users should consider.

Blessings of SNS

Although sometimes the negative impacts and consequences of SNS overshadow its positive appeals but the incredible growth of SNS clearly indicates that there must be some reasonable goodness instilled in it.

- (i) *Effective Communication*: SNS through its convenient and easy to use tools like blogs, forums, and e-mails, has been leading the whole globe to become one society

that is more connected than ever before. Friends and families, and coworkers living far away from one another can stay close using the SNS platform even with the live audio-visual appeal just a click away. There could be found thousands of instances where SNS has facilitated reestablishing the communication with a long lost friend that could ever not be possible without SNS. It also provides with a comparatively rich and fulfilling social life to those who are isolated by disability or unavoidable environment issues.

- (ii) *Resources for Education and Research:* Students, teachers and professionals are some of the highly benefited groups in a better and effective manner with respect to the conventional way of getting similar benefits. Positive affiliation with SNS has become a commendable institutional feature to claim worth. For this reason, many educational institutions keep links to SNSs on their webpage that will lead the web surfers to the discussions in the SNSs from where they can perceive the image of that institution. Researchers and scientists now can collaborate with each other around the world most effectively. Getting information from across the world has become possible and faster. Resources are now available in digital form even if availability in the physical version is still beyond possibility.
- (iii) *Business Intelligence:* Possibly the business world has been enjoying the highest level of benefits from SNS. With the help of intelligent collaborative filtering approaches utilizing advanced data mining techniques the business world has been overcoming the problem of attention economy and been successfully delivering their messages to the target customers in the most effective manner. The internet marketers who use information from SNS can better analyze customers' demands and expectations as information are coming directly from the customers. SNS has created a platform where the business world can get real feedback from the users as they give information after being convinced. It has also opened doors for many new innovative business opportunities that the world even could not think of earlier. Consumer behavior analysis, employee recruitment, search engine marketing and optimization, and many more innovative usages have become possible and easier after the emergence of SNS. The platform has been used by many firms to sustain in the current global economic recession as it facilitated cost savings in several ways, some of which are online campaigning and viral marketing (marketing techniques that use pre-existing social networks for commercial purposes).

Worries of SNS

SNS has become one of the most interesting topics to both the researchers and the social scientists because of its long-term impacts in multiple dimensions. Some of the worries that attracted the attention of those think-tanks are briefly discussed below.

- (i) *Personal Information Goes Public:* In every SNS there are embedded threats of divulging users' personal information and theft of identity. Some international secret agencies' violation of laws and the abuse of controversial patriot act are dazzling proof of such risks. Personal information stored in the SNS includes details on religion, relationship, hobbies, views on politics and many other issues. Combination of these details makes it compelling and interesting but at the same time potentially dangerous. A multi-hour outage on Facebook once caused a fault with the site that let some users view other's personal site mail but surprisingly the Facebook management did not consider it to be a hacking. Using the detail information available on SNS, it can be located where the user lives that sometimes might cause personal security problems.
- (ii) *Shock for the Students:* The meaning of the word 'friend' is changing for many students and this change puts them at risk in several ways. They have very little knowledge about how much they are being marketed to; how their purchasing decisions and attitudes are being manipulated; how their personal information is used, and even how valuable that personal information is to other people. Very often students realize that they cannot control the flow and waste lot of time online and at times they are puzzled to get the false sense of privacy.
- (iii) *Wastage of Working Hours:* This has become a major concern for most employers due to the resulting substantial productivity loss caused by wasting working hours online with SNS activities. A research found that on an average Facebook alone cost \$5 billion a year in Australian business (Fisher, 2008).
- (iv) *Social Disparity:* As SNS requires difficult electronic communication at times, it increases the existing digital divide phenomenon and the technologically challenged people become the worst victim of it. Some users of SNS use their access to SNS as a way for creating social capital that occasionally demoralizes others.
- (v) *Identity Fraud:* Identity fraud has become a common trouble for users who are usually the popular faces in any society. One embedded flaw of SNS is - no one can be sure of who they are interacting and conversing with. This anonymity adds an unusual twist to socialization as people can essentially be whomever they desire. Although most of the people are truthful with their personalities but unfortunately some develop online personas with false pretenses.
- (vi) *Distortion in Social Value System:*
 "...91 percent of all social networking teens say they use the sites to stay in touch with friends they see frequently, while 82 percent use the sites to stay in touch with friends they rarely see in person." (Lenhart, 2007:1)

Electronic interactions sometimes displace the social interactions keeping people apart. SNS has created such a convenient platform that people generally lack the drive to actually interact face to face. As people are social beings, removing the direct social interactions might affect their social development, especially if started

at a young age. Sometimes it also changes the way people usually interact and these changes might eventually affect the evolution of social interaction as meeting people in the SNS removes personal touches.

- (vii) *Communication Skill Gets Affected*: One aspect of SNS that sometimes can be detrimental to the society is that, dependence on these SNSs often leads to poor interpersonal communications. Comments coming out from users of SNS are sometimes more spontaneous but less thoughtful. Many such drawbacks might lead to misunderstandings, arguments, and eventually a degradation of conversations that could easily be avoided by a phone call or talking in person.
- (viii) *Obsession Factor Disruptions*: SNS might lead to excessive computer use that might lead to a dysfunctional lifestyle where other important activities like maintaining healthy sleeping and eating habits, and spending time with family and friends, are almost completely ignored. In 2003, researchers of the City University of New York found that young children who excessively used the computer for over 8 hours a week spent significantly less time outdoor playing or taking part in other beneficial activities. They were also found to have substantially heavier body mass index.

Critiques on Facebook

The famous SNS Facebook has undergone tremendous growth rate around the world since its inception. Among all other SNSs Facebook now leads the market and the data presented in table 1 clearly presents that dominance in a comparative manner and thus justifies my single selection for critical review.

Table 1: Global Growth of Selected SNS during June 2007 to June 2008

Demographics:	Coverage: Worldwide Age Group: Over 15 SNS Usage Location: Home and Work Locations		
	Total Unique Visitors (000)		
	June 2007	June 2008	% Change
Social Networking	464,437	580,510	25%
Facebook.com	52,167	132,105	153%
MySpace.com	114,147	117,582	3%
Hi5.com	28,174	56,367	100%
Friendster.com	24,675	37,080	50%
Orkut	24,120	34,028	41%
Bebo.com	18,200	24,017	32%
Skyrock Network	17,638	21,041	19%

Source: comScore, Inc., 2008.

In December 2004, it had nearly one million active users but in the consecutive years till September 2009, the figure became more than 5.5 million, over 12 million, more than 50 million, over 100 million and over 300 million respectively (Facebook, 2009). With this sporadic growth the degree of criticism has also been increasing among the researchers as well as many users and non-users. The global rise of Facebook has become a matter for concern rather than excitement as people have started raising critical questions like: does Facebook really connect people? Doesn't it rather disconnect us, since instead of doing something enjoyable such as talking and eating and dancing and drinking with my friends, I am merely sending them little ungrammatical notes and amusing photos in cyberspace, while chained to my desk?

Facebook has been criticized specially due to sacrificing the privacy of users and child safety; improper advertising scripts, data mining (analyzing data to figure out individual's attitude) without customers' consent, and difficulty in permanently deleting contents from the server. Some changes like Facebook's terms of use that removed the clause - detailing automatic expiry of deleted content, in the upgraded version launched in 2008 were also criticized. In 2007, many companies removed their advertisements from the site as those were also displayed on the pages of controversial individuals and groups. The SNS is alleged for too much advertisement related to the promotion of alcohol and this dangerous act of exposing the younger generation to alcohol advertising is rapidly increasing. In many cases several issues regarding censorship, both on and off the site were criticized by some users and some non-users as well. Facebook has also been sued several times for violating intellectual property rights.

The following highlights briefly present how the real world reacted occasionally with respect to the impacts created by Facebook.

- Burma, Bhutan, and Iran (until 2009) have banned the website.
- In November 2007, Facebook was blocked by the Syrian government on the premise that it promoted attacks on the authorities (Reuters, 2007).
- Numerous reports are appearing of job candidates not being hired and employees being fired because of information found about them on social networking sites (Humphries, 2007).
- On July 7, 2009, Facebook was blocked by the Chinese government on the premise that future riots in XinJiang could be organized through online social networks.
- Since it violates many school boards' terms of use for the internet along with local and state laws, many school boards in North America, Europe and Oceania that run elementary through high schools have blocked access to Facebook.

Implications for Bangladesh

Bangladesh has no way but to be exposed to the mainstream technology system due to the pressure of globalization. With a vivid presence of access to technology asymmetry and dominating digital divide and its consequences, the country should have considered the lack of technological readiness. The issue is also addressed by Dr. Felix Reed-Tsochas, director of complex systems at InSIS at Oxford University:

“...There is an acute lack of understanding of the driving forces and mechanisms behind the way we use these communication tools that we now all take for granted. We have little understanding of how recent forms of social interaction like facebook and Twitter influence individuals and societies as existing knowledge in this area is fragmented.” (2009:2)

According to a report by alexa.com (2009) in Bangladesh the top 10 mostly accessed sites are Facebook, google.com, google.com.bd, yahoo, blogger.com, YouTube, Windows live, Wikipedia, Rapidshare and *Prothom Alo*. This clearly reflects the dominance of SNS as Facebook ranks first in the list. Although the netizens are comfortable with SNS as most of them have grown up with the internet but they represent a small portion of the total population engrossed in technology based systems. The parental generation is generally not adapted with the technology embedded systems and thus parental control faces the difficulty of perceiving the consequences of SNS involvements especially in case of the younger generation. Even institutional security systems are also sometimes at a stake. Website hacking of the country's one of the top security forces by some university students is a burning instance of that. The policy makers and the institutional entities should have considered the long term issues involved in the inappropriately controlled SNS platform as we have significant number of technologically challenged people with a few capable but aggressive information technology savvy geniuses.

Facebook has surely spirited the users in their social as well as business lives as they are enjoying many innovative applications in the SNS that eliminated the problems of distance and time requirement. Many users have the basic knowledge about how to use the fundamental default services from the SNS but due to poor knowledge about how to configure the SNS to customize privacy feature and others, SNS has become a trouble for many. Sometimes this leads to a growing confusion between our weak ties and our strong ties in the society. Keeping the positive aspects of SNS in mind we have to be very careful about the long term impacts of it so that this single communication tool does not appear fatal for our unique culture and heritage. Therefore sincere careful control measure should be imposed in case of younger generation's involvements in it.

In business arena, Facebook is not extensively used in this country rather some of our software experts have been working as outsourced developer of some applications for the

SNS. However, consumers are now more empowered due to their affiliation with this SNS. They now have been enjoying and utilizing the opportunities to share experiences and opinions both with other users and the respective companies. Business here can make good use of this communication to reach customers easily as well as spreading customized messages with ease and more effectiveness. This decreasing asymmetry of information between buyer and seller will ultimately put pressure on the business sector to maintain quality and follow customers' expectations resulting more satisfied customers but competitive and challenging market environment. Nevertheless, malpractices through the SNS might also consequence unexpected market failure and high degree of inefficiency. A recent rumor spread in early January 2010 through Facebook regarding informal stock market information created tension among shareholders and the watchdogs like Security and Exchange Commission and Dhaka Stock Exchange. Although strict institutional control measures resolved that market anxiety but it should be treated as a warning for the watchdogs so that activities of SNS no more create any such abnormality in business or in social life. A hope for this country is that the mobile commerce endeavor naming 'cellbazar' is now booming and similar innovative internet based business approaches might utilize the power of SNS as a communication media.

Conclusion

Scientists strongly believe that internet is changing how our brains develop as we get older. They also found that it affects almost everything from how we associate information to even how we socialize. Neuroscientist Susan Greenfield argues that social networking sites, video games and other electronic media are doing more harm than good. According to an interview with the Daily Mail, Susan Greenfield said:

"...such input may be 'infantilizing' the brain, creating a generation of children who are attracted by buzzing noises and bright lights, who have a small attention span and who live for the moment." (O'Brien, 2009:1)

Preventive measures should be better checks against the dark sides of SNS regarding social aspects and business opportunities rather than restraining the netizens from using innovative communicative tools. We should analyze SNS issues and adopt lessons from others as these issues are new to us and sometimes we are not expert enough to determine better solutions due to the lack of experiences. Global issues might show us ways as in case of online issues it is the whole globe the technology can reach that should be considered as the home ground.

SNS causes social ties go public and hence we have to be careful about individual and institutional privacy. Know-how regarding the privacy settings of the SNS should be the first lesson before using it. We also should be very conservative in unveiling personal information that might enable others trace our location or might make it easier for the

internet marketers to sketch our behavioral patterns that we might not like to be used commercially. We must remember that as Facebook and MySpace are two of the largest SNSs, these are the main targets of the hackers, spammers and online predators. SNS can be fun, but it should never be a replacement for good old-fashioned traditions. Experienced institutional monitoring, careful involvement and intelligent usage might reduce the risks and can make SNS a miracle in promoting sound social tie and effective online business.

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